

THE CHALLENGES OF THE PANDEMIC ON A GLOBAL AUTOMOTIVE IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper has the purpose to present the biggest challenges during pandemic period for automotive industry and examples from a global automotive industry of a standardization project

Methodology/approach – The authors of this article, carried out a research study on how the Covid-19 Pandemic affected the automotive industry around the world and came with specific examples from their daily activity. We used general methods of analysis, comparison and case study.

Findings – Challenges can be great opportunities if they are viewed from the right angle. The companies, especially industrial companies must keep pace with the development of technologies and customer demand

Research limitations/implications – The paper is limited to automotive industry, larger research is necessary for a general conclusion of the researched topic.

Practical implications – As a project member in Romania - where planning and pilot-run was done for inspection improvement project, taking decisions in a critical time, as Pandemic was, is an important step to personal and company development.

Originality/value – The lesson-learned during this situation can be applied in other plants of the company, or in other automotive companies. The study was done based on inspection process, but the challenges described are applicable for other projects too.

Key words: Challenges, Automotive, Adaptation, Improvement, Opportunities

Introduction

The Covid Pandemic changed the face of the whole world, having a big impact on the planet, impacting the human life, industries and the economy. Among the most affected sectors, we have the automotive industry, which is one of the most dominant contributors to European economy. Automotive industry ecosystem creates a workplace for 14,6 million Europeans, representing 6,7 percent of total European Union employment becoming one of the pillars of the industries. (ACEA, 2020)

The goal of the paper is to describe the biggest challenges for automotive industry during Covid Pandemic and in the second part of the paper, the challenges of a particular case: a standardization project for a global automotive company and how these challenges were handled to progress the implementation with a positive result. Findings show how important it is to see how challenges can become great opportunities and how important it is for companies to keep improving and developing their technologies. Described challenges are a part of a study, where actual global situation of inspection process is analyzed based on different factors.

Pandemic Challenges for Automotive Industry

Covid-19 hit the automotive industry directly and the long-term effects cannot be predicted. After 2 years we are certain of a few things: taking at least six months to buy a new ordered car, even if people are insecure and they are not investing so much in luxury products, as cars.

According to a Deloitte article, "The Futures of Mobility After COVID-19" (Corwin, Zarif, Berdichevskiy, and Pankratz, 2020), four different scenarios are explored in post-coronavirus world: 1) passing storm,

2) sunrise in the east, 3) good company and 4) lone-wolves: have a three-to-five-years time frame. These scenarios are related to how things looked before pandemic in four different fields such as leadership, priority, markets and personal-data.

According to a study of PWC (2018), the biggest challenging factors for automotive industry are:

- consumer demand (risk of consumer confidence loss with negative impact revenues and profits of automakers),
- capital issues (prioritizing operational activities and thus limiting spends on R&D on other projects or innovations),
- corporate strategy (decisions about manufacturing rationalization and possible exit from unprofitable markets),
- supply chains (liquidity problems of suppliers, disruption of global supply chains and complications for entire global automotive ecosystem),
- issues of retail companies (loss of demand may impact the structure of retail sector as companies will react to market changes)

Six big challenges affect the automotive industry around the world:

Fig. 1. Top 6 challenges of the Automotive Industry (Saipriya Iyer, 2022)

Pandemic Challenges for a standardization project in an automotive company

Standardization project: Improvement of Inspection process in Hirschmann Automotive

Before the pandemic, the global automotive company started an improvement project for a process standardization. The plan of the project was to create a plan of improvements, to have a pilot-run in the Romanian plant then to implement it in all company's factories: China, Morocco, Czech, Mexico, Austria and Germany.

The project addressed is the improvement and standardization process of the final product inspection. The inspection activity is present in all Hirschmann Automotive factories since the first product is made by inspecting its characteristics. Over time, these characteristics have multiplied and diversified based

on the new characteristics imposed primarily by customers, the technologization and diversification of processes, the change of production factors, the diversification of the human factor, the implementation of new standards imposed by the field of activity, as well as other financial or cultural influences.

Inspection process refers to activity of checking the conformance of the produced products according to the customer's requirements. These activities are examining, testing, measuring or gauging, depending by type of products. The results are compared with specified requirements.

Based on these imposed changes, each factory built and adapted its sorting process to meet its own local objectives. With the development of factories and globalization, common customers began to demand the same method and approach regardless of the manufacturing plant, which led to the realization that standardization of the inspection process globally is necessary.

Starting from the idea of standardizing the product inspection process within this global company and taking into account the diversity of manufactured products, the culture of the countries they belong to, manufacturing conditions, etc. the most important step is to identify what the current situation is in each factory. For this identification, a quick action with maximum benefits would have been a visit to each factory. Unfortunately, due to the unfavorable travel conditions imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic, these very beneficial visits were impossible. Precisely for this reason, the team had to find another alternative through which they could find out information. In order to solve this situation and advance the project, the approach of a questionnaire was identified in which sorting coordinators can participate, where there are also quality managers, towards the idea of having at the end some relevant questions and answers that can be compared and used for development and standardization of the researched process. The main objective of the questionnaire is to identify using the same questions for all survey members what the current status of the sorting process in all Hirschmann Automotive plants is and in addition what are the major similarities and differences between the plants, to which is added the identification of the main need for improvement and standardization. Out of about 15 platforms checked, only two were compatible with the needs of the project, including Google Form and Survicate, most of the others could have been used after an initial payment. Of these, Survicate (<https://survicate.com/>) was chosen because although Google Form seemed easier to use, it is not accessible from the company's security platform.

The type of survey chosen is factual data, also called administrative questionnaire, through which data, situations and facts can be evaluated. To start the survey, I asked some basic questions: "Where?", "Who?", "Why?", "How?", "What?", "How much?". The next step was not to answer the questions, but to write down the main elements (resources) that lead to and answer these questions and are common to every factory regardless of the manufactured products. So, starting with these basic questions, we identified the main factors for inspection process:

- "Where?" - *Sorting area* - the place that is defined to be used strictly for this product inspection process
- "Who?" - *Human resources* - Area coordinator, if any; operators designated for inspection; the other support functions - logistics employees, quality engineers
- "How?" - *Equipment* - all material resources used: tables, chairs, boxes, lamps and special measuring and checking equipment
- *Documents* - All forms and documents used to perform the sort
- "How much?" - *Time, Costs and Reporting* - All sorting activity is perceived as a service added to the products, because it is not a manufacturing process that adds anything physically to the products, precisely for this reason, this process is "measured" by operator verification time on a specific product/quantity, then converted into costs and reporting these amounts to management and customers when appropriate.

Hello, let's improve together the system Hirschmann Global Sorting Overview	01	HUMAN RESOURCES Which is the target for sorting operators? For example, to have dedicated...	13
Short introduction Your Hirschmann Plant	02	EQUIPMENTS Do you have in the sorting area dedicated/ specially created tables/ work...	14
Short introduction Please write your name and your role in the company?	03	EQUIPMENTS What additional auxiliary equipment/ area are necessary for the sorting ...	15
How important do you think it is to have a standard sorting system in the company?	04	DOCUMENTS What are the used and dedicated documents (procedure, form, etc) used...	16
AREA Do you have a dedicated sorting/ inspection area in your plant? If yes ple...	05	DOCUMENTS Who is responsible to prepare the inspection instruction?	17
AREA Are there any products in your plant with special production conditions o...	06	DOCUMENTS How you evaluate the idea to have the digital inspection instruction, on a...	18
AREA What do you consider being the main objective/ target for the sorting/ ins...	07	TIME, COST AND REPORTING Which are the sorting results for 2021? Total costs and total sorted quant...	19
HUMAN RESOURCES Do you have a dedicated sorting coordinator? If yes, please name a few o...	08	TIME, COST AND REPORTING Do you evaluate frequently the costs of the sorting activities? If yes, how ...	20
HUMAN RESOURCES In your plant do you have dedicated sorting workers (who's main job is to...	09	TIME, COST AND REPORTING Which is the actual exit criteria for a sorting? (when a product is eliminat...	21
HUMAN RESOURCES Are the sorting/ inspection workers included in the competence/ polyvalen...	10	PRODUCTION FEEDBACK & ACTION PLAN How is the communication defined between inspection area and product...	22
HUMAN RESOURCES How have you hired the dedicated sorting operators? (example: by HR sp...	11	PRODUCTION FEEDBACK & ACTION PLAN Is there an action plan or a dedicated board on which the top failures are...	23
HUMAN RESOURCES Who is training the operators on each inspection instruction?	12	PRODUCTION FEEDBACK & ACTION PLAN Are sorting results included in any daily meeting of the management? Ple...	24
		PRODUCTION FEEDBACK & ACTION PLAN Are there any other points which you consider necessary to take in consi...	25

Fig. 2. Questions from the global questionnaire (www.survicate.com)

Following the questionnaire, except for one factory where the entire manufacturing chain is technological, and the potential for deviation from standards is minimal, all factories completed the answers to the questions.

On the first three elements: the sorting area, human resources and equipment, it is obvious that the necessity forced all factories to have these three resources available in one form or another, but enough to carry out their activity towards the fulfillment of the current objectives: sorting and delivery of compliant products to customers.

Regarding the last resources surveyed, it is very easy to see that it is not a general standard, there is no system that helps factories to firstly document the activity, and then to evaluate it, finally to improve the processes that imposes the need for sorting and which at the same time would streamline both production and the costs currently allocated by the insufficiently monitored sorting system.

Challenges of Inspection process because of Covid-19

When the pandemic started in Romania, the improvement process was only in the planning phase, and in that time we faced many challenges that will influence the project's progress in this early stage:

Fig. 3. Top Challenges for project influences by Covid Pandemic (Hirschmann Automotive)

- Travel limitations – the most important obstacle for the development of the project. For a global project, travelling in all countries to meet the project members and make an overview was considered essential.

For this limitation, online meetings were a great solution. In the company, before pandemic the online meetings were not very used as much as phone calls, emails, personal visits. Being an old company, the big step to digitalization was not considered necessary, but being the only possibility, it was warmly embraced.

- Manufacturing shutdowns -Starting with the manufacturing factories in China, all over the world, companies were closed for a period of time. These operating breaks were also present in Hirschmann Automotive in some plants, including Romania's plant. The shutdown period was not so long compared to other companies, but the insecurity in the world and implicitly in the company imposed a pause in the project until the full return of work in the factory, this it means more than 6 months of postponed timelines.
- Communication – being a global project, the common language was English. Communication is vital to develop valuable interpersonal relationships. An effective way of communicating is more than essential to develop productivity and maintain long-term relationships, communication takes place in two plans: a content plan (10%) and a relationship plan (90%) therefor travelling and binding relationships during visits were considered so essential. The language of communication is the biggest barrier in an intercultural communication, but not the most fundamental. People who do not speak the same language or do not speak the language well, may have difficulties communicating. Sometimes, even those who share the same language can understand and perceive in a different form what is spoken to them, given the experience and knowledge of the topic discussed. The equivalence of the concepts expressed can take different forms than in the communicated language, i.e. English in this case.

Following this standardization project and all the online meetings, from personal experience I can admit that without a personal knowledge of the interlocutors, without creating a small relationship, communication was difficult and often, although the discussed subject was repeated, it was still necessary to clarify the same topic at least 2-3 times to remain with the same idea all participants.

- Different time zone – The main element in a team is communication, followed by availability and being present for meetings and project progress. Time zone differences can be a major impediment if they are not taken into account when a project is planned and organized.

According to some internet opinions, the pandemic is a good reason to eliminate the different time zones. If we are thinking about globalization and communication between multiple countries, this proposal can be a good idea, but from my point of view the reasons are not enough.

No matter how important it was to communicate with the Hirschmann factories at the same time to discuss the commonalities, this was impossible due to the time zone difference. For example, the difference between Romania and Mexico is -8 hours and between Romania and China is +8 hours, in conclusion the difference between Mexico and China is 14 hours. This difference has prevented joint online meetings between factories in Europe and the other continents of the world. They ultimately affected the communication and extended the project period, as the same topics were addressed with each, as well as the questions between them. For the future, we are thinking to implement a private chat for each project where team members can leave text or voice messages to other colleagues in a simple and easy way.

A good organization, based on difference time zone in a multicultural project, can make money when you are sleeping.

- IT Resources – in addition to the standardization of the process, there was the implementation of electronic tablets at each workstation. These tablets should be used for the digitization of forms and process documents. The challenge imposed by the Covid pandemic was when we tried to purchase these electronic equipments because the brand chosen for Romania does not deliver to Morocco. This impediment could have been solved by purchasing all the tablets in Romania and delivering them to the other six Hirschmann locations in the world, but the warranty only covered Europe at best and the travel and replacement costs would have exceeded the planned costs, without considering the time spent for these movements. The consequences of these situations lead to a decrease in the company's productivity, efficiency and proposed results.

Using the presented challenges as lesson-learned for the next projects, Hirschmann Automotive or other companies can have a positive and valuable inputs for their next projects.

Discussion and conclusions

To adapt to changing and challenging times, automotive experts are required to adapt and educate themselves with the latest trends and technologies. As Joe Vitale, mentioned in an article of Deloitte, "Understanding the impact of COVID-19, Automotive sector", automotive companies should take in consideration the next practical steps to mitigate the impact of the pandemic: identification and prioritization of cost-out measures, optimization of working capital, revising forecast assumptions, prioritizing downside scenarios given the current level of market uncertainty, identifying sources of collateral and additional solutions, focusing on employee safety and care. (Vitale, 2020)

During the project directly affected by the pandemic period, several scenarios were considered, including stopping the project until the situation in the automotive industry becomes more stable. The challenges taken individually and their attempt to find suitable solutions to continue the project improved the vision and encouraged the team to progress with the new decisions, which in the end proved to be successful. Through a primary analysis of this questionnaire, the need to standardize how a sorting instruction is applied, then how the resulting data is collected, analyzed and used in action plans for improvement, is evident. The major problem in this standardization process was the application of local documents in each plant, which indirectly leads to differences in the application of methods, of different interpretation both by global management and by common customers between plants.

It is very interesting, how at the beginning we started from the premise: "how can we all do the same thing in the same way?", then after researching, developing and implementing a system, we concluded that it would be best to ask the same question in a different form, namely: "how can we accommodate the differences we know will exist anyway".

In the end, this research shows the idea that any challenge can be an opportunity if it is viewed from a different perspective with the right attitude, knowing the risks, sharing the knowledge, having an open mind and following the main purpose. Staying competitive, rethink their short-term playbook, applying lesson learned and integrating smart are only a few of the next steps for automotive industry pushed by Covid-19 pandemic.

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